

Refractometric Studies on Solute Aggregation, Solute Solvent and Charge Transfer Interactions of Some Metal Acetylacetonates with Iodine

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Solute aggregation, solute-solvent and charge-transfer interactions of acetylacetonates of Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III), Co(III), VO(IV), Th(IV) and Zr(IV) with iodine have been studied in carbon tetrachloride using refractometric and differential refractometric techniques. It has been observed that the acceptor has greater contribution in total 30% solute aggregation than donors. On the basis of equilibrium constant (K_1) and extent of electronic polarization (α) data, the solute-solvent interaction has been noted. The values of α and k (the maximum deviation from the additive line) have been discussed in terms of electronic polarizability and their use in the calculation of dipole moment have been explored. These data further support on the pseudo-aromatic character of metal acetylacetonate chelate rings.

WE have reported through spectrophotometric¹, conductometric², dielectric³ and refractometric⁴ studies that some metal acetylacetonates form molecular complexes with iodine by the donation of π -electrons of these chelate rings to σ^* -orbital of iodine. Thus, in order to provide further evidence on the pseudo-aromatic character of acetylacetonate chelate rings, the solute aggregation, solute-solvent and charge-transfer interactions of acetylacetonates of Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III), Co(III), VO(IV), Th(IV) and Zr(IV) with iodine have been studied using some recent methods^{5,6} developed in our laboratory by modifying the method of Yoshida and Osawa⁷.

Experimental

The methods of experimentation are essentially the same as reported earlier⁴. The acetylacetonates of Zr(IV) and Th(IV) have been prepared as reported in the literature^{8,9}. In order to study through Yoshida and Osawa's method⁷ and Sahai *et al* methods^{5,6}, a little modification in the method of experimentation has been made which is as follows:

The refractive indices have been measured by Bausch and Lomb refractometer with an accuracy of ± 0.0002 . All the measurements were made at 30°. The refractive indices were measured for three sets of solutions: in first set, the refractive indices of donors (n_D) were measured, in second set, the refractive indices of acceptor solution (n_A) were noted, in third set, the refractive indices of mixed solution (donor+acceptor) were noted. The equimolar solutions of donors [M(acac)_n, where M = Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Co(III), Fe(III), VO(IV), Th(IV) and Zr(IV)] and acceptor (iodine) in carbon tetrachloride were mixed and the refractive indices (n) were measured. In this procedure, the total

volume of the solution was kept constant and the volumes of donor and acceptor were varied.

The equilibrium constant (K_1) and extent of electronic polarization (α) of molecular complexes have been calculated using equations (1-4) recently developed by Sahai *et al*^{6,10,11}.

$$\delta\phi/C_D^0 = \{K_1 C_A^0 / \alpha (1 + K_1 C_A^0)\} - \{K_1 \delta\phi / (1 + K_1 C_A^0)^2\} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\Delta\phi_a/C_D^0 = \{K_1 C_A^0 / \alpha (1 + K_1 C_A^0)\} - \{K_1 \Delta\phi_a / (1 + K_1 C_A^0)^2\} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\Delta\phi_d/C_D^0 = \{K_1 C_A^0 / \alpha (1 + K_1 C_A^0)\} - \{K_1 \Delta\phi_d / (1 + K_1 C_A^0)^2\} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}/C_D^0 = \{K_1 C_A^0 / \alpha (1 + K_1 C_A^0)\} - \{K_1 \Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}} / (1 + K_1 C_A^0)^2\} \quad \dots (4)$$

In these equations C_D^0 and C_A^0 are the initial concentrations of donor (D) and acceptor (A), respectively. $\delta\phi$, $\Delta\phi_a$ and $\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}$ have their usual meanings and have been calculated as reported earlier^{6,10,11,12}. $\Delta\phi_d$ may be calculated from equation* (5).

$$\Delta\phi_d = 10^3 (\phi - \phi_d) = 6000(n - n_D)n_D / (n_D^2 + 2) \quad \dots (5)$$

where the notations have their usual meanings as reported earlier^{6,10,11,12}. As expected from equations(1-4) the plots of $\delta\phi$ vs $\delta\phi/C_D^0$, $\Delta\phi_a$ vs $\Delta\phi_a/C_D^0$, $\Delta\phi_d$ vs $\Delta\phi_d/C_D^0$ and $\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}$ vs $\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}/C_D^0$ were linear with a slope = $-K_1/(1+K_1C_A^0)^2$ and intercept $K_1 C_A^0 / \alpha (1 + K_1 C_A^0)$ (Figs. 1 and 2).

Refractometric and differential refractometric titration techniques have indicated 1:1 stoichiometry of these complexes (Figs. 3 and 4).

* $\Delta\phi$ of equation (3) of our previous paper⁴ has now been denoted as $\Delta\phi_a$ because $\Delta\phi_a$ was taken as reference. The change in notations were made because equation (3) of the present paper was not considered in our earlier paper⁴. Therefore presently only equation (5) is given to evaluate the value of $\Delta\phi_d$ and $\Delta\phi_a$ may be calculated by equation (5) of our earlier papers^{4,5,6,10,11,12}.

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The K_1 has also been calculated by using Yoshida and Osawa's⁷ equation (6).

$$K_1 = 2 \sqrt{k} \{ \sqrt{k}(C+C') - (C+kC') \} / (C-kC')^2 \dots (6)$$

where C and C' are the maximum concentration of both the systems and k is the maximum deviation from the additive line when molar ratio of solutes is plotted against square of refractive index (n^2). The K_1 has also been calculated by modified Yoshida and Osawa's method as recently developed by Sahai *et al*^{5,6}. In these methods, instead of a plot of n^2 vs molar ratio of solutes, $\Delta\phi_a$ or $\Delta\phi_d$ or $\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}$ is plotted against molar ratio of solutes. These values have been calculated as reported earlier^{6,10-12}. A representative plot of $\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}$ vs molar ratio of solutes indicating 1 : 1 stoichiometry of these complexes is shown in Fig. 5. The stoichiometry of these complexes has also been calculated by plotting $\phi_D C_A^0$ (or $\phi_D / \Delta\phi_{DA} C_A^0$) against X_D (mole fraction of donor), the maximum occurs at $X_D = n/(1+n)$ (Fig. 6). At this maxima, if $n=1$, then K_1 may be calculated by equation (7)¹³.

$$K_1 = (\phi_D / \Delta\phi_{DA}) / (C_D^0) (1 - \phi_D / \Delta\phi_{DA})^2 \dots (7)$$

Fig. 1. Plots of $\delta\phi$ vs $\delta\phi/C_B$, $\Delta\phi_d$ vs $\Delta\phi_d/C_D$ and $\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}$ vs $\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}/C_D^0$ for molecular complexes of $\text{Th}(\text{acac})_4$ and $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_4$ with iodine in carbon tetrachloride at 30° .

- $\text{Th}(\text{acac})_4\text{-I}_2$] $\delta\phi$ vs $\delta\phi/C_D^\circ$
- $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_4\text{-I}_2$] $\delta\phi$ vs $\delta\phi/C_D^\circ$
- ▲—▲—▲ $\text{Th}(\text{acac})_4\text{-I}_2$] $\Delta\phi_d$ vs $\Delta\phi_d/C_D^\circ$
- △—△—△ $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_4\text{-I}_2$] $\Delta\phi_d$ vs $\Delta\phi_d/C_D^\circ$
- $\text{Th}(\text{acac})_4\text{-I}_2$] $\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}$ vs $\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}/C_D^\circ$
- $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_4\text{-I}_2$] $\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}$ vs $\Delta\Omega_{C_{DA}}/C_D^\circ$

Fig. 2. Plots of $\Delta\phi_d$ vs $\Delta\phi_d/C_B$ for molecular complexes of metal acetylacetonates with iodine in carbon tetrachloride.

- $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3\text{-I}_2$ □—□—□ $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3\text{-I}_2$
- △—△—△ $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3\text{-I}_2$ ○—○—○ $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_3\text{-I}_2$
- ▲—▲—▲ $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3\text{-I}_2$ ■—■—■ $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_4\text{-I}_2$
- ⊕—⊕—⊕ $\text{Th}(\text{acac})_4\text{-I}_2$

Fig. 3. Refractometric and differential refractometric titration curves for the molecular complex of $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_4$ with iodine indicating 1 : 1 stoichiometry.

Fig. 4. Refractometric and differential refractometric titration curves for the molecular complex of $\text{Th}(\text{acac})_4$ with iodine showing 1 : 1 stoichiometry.

Fig. 6. Plots of X_D versus $\Delta\phi_D/\Delta\phi_{DA} C_A^0$ for molecular complexes of metal acetylacetonates with iodine indicating 1 : 1 stoichiometry in carbon tetrachloride.

●—●—● $\text{Th}(\text{acac})_4\text{-I}_2$ ■—■—■ $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_4\text{-I}_2$
 ▲—▲—▲ $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3\text{-I}_2$ ○—○—○ $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_3\text{-I}_2$

Fig. 5. Plots of molar ratio of solutes versus $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$ indicating 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the molecular complexes of metal acetylacetonates with iodine in carbon tetrachloride.

0.6 × 10⁻³ M 1.0 × 10⁻³ M
 Th(acac)₄-I₂ ○—○—○ ●—●—●
 Zr(acac)₄-I₂ □—□—□ ■—■—■

where $\Delta\phi_{DA} = \phi_{DA} - \phi_{SD}$ and $\phi_{SD} = \phi - \phi_D$. These values have been calculated as reported earlier^{4-6,10-13}. The contribution of donor (SA_d) and acceptor (SA_a) in total 30% solute aggregation for weak complexes $[\text{Be}(\text{acac})_2\text{-I}_2]$, have been calculated through equations (8) and (9) respectively⁶.

$$SA_a = 30 \cdot \Delta K_a / \Delta K_{da} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$SA_d = 30 \cdot \Delta K_a / \Delta K_{da} \quad \dots (9)$$

where,

$\Delta K_{da} = K_{n^2} - K_{\Delta\Omega C_{DA}}$ = total 30% solute aggregation; $\Delta K_a = K_{n^2} - K_{\Delta\phi_a}$ = solute aggregation due to acceptor; $\Delta K_{da} = (\Delta K_{da} - \Delta K_a)$ = solute aggregation due to donor,

and

$K_{n^2} = K_1$ calculated from the plot of n^2 vs molar ratio of solutes or from equation (1); $K_{\Delta\phi_a} = K_1$ calculated from the plot of $\Delta\phi_a$ vs molar ratio of solutes or from equation (2); $K_{\Delta\phi_{da}} = K_1$ calculated from the plot of $\Delta\phi_{da}$ vs molar ratio of solutes or from equation (3); $K_{\Delta\Omega C_{DA}} = K_1$ calculated from the plot of $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$ vs molar ratio of solutes or from equation (4).

Results and Discussion

Charge-transfer interaction and solute aggregation: An appreciable increase in $\delta\phi$, $\Delta\phi_a$, $\Delta\phi_d$ and $\Delta\Omega C_{DA}$ values with the increase of donor concentration and keeping the acceptor concentration constant confirm the charge-transfer interaction

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT (K_1) SOLUTE AGGREGATION AND EXTENT OF ELECTRONIC POLARIZATION (α) DATA FOR 1 : 1 MOLECULAR COMPLEXES OF SOME METAL ACETYLACETONATES WITH IODINE IN CARBON TETRACHLORIDE AT 30°

	Equilibrium Constant (K_1) l. mole ⁻¹				Extent of Electronic Polarization, $\alpha \times 10^4$				SA _d	SA _a
	From Eq. 1	From Eq. 2	From Eq. 3	From Eq. 4	From Eq. 1	From Eq. 2	From Eq. 3	From Eq. 4		
	Be(acac) ₃ -I ₂	41.66	37.04	35.00	30.00	11.76	12.31	12.38		
Al(acac) ₃ -I ₂	384.61	238.09	220.00	174.41	0.74	0.64	0.62	0.75		
Fe(acac) ₃ -I ₂	454.54	344.82	310.00	256.41	0.75	0.83	0.80	1.04		
Cr(acac) ₃ -I ₂	903.02	800.00	800.00	833.33	0.91	0.89	0.86	1.63		
VO(acac) ₃ -I ₂	952.02	909.00	930.00	952.38	1.74	1.61	0.95	2.31		
Co(acac) ₃ -I ₂	1052.63	952.38	915.00	1176.47	1.74	1.70	0.92	2.76		
Zr(acac) ₄ -I ₂	1420.00	1240.00	1220.00	1175.00	3.30	3.10	2.95	2.90		
Th(acac) ₄ -I ₂	2500.00	2230.00	2200.00	2130.00	3.53	3.40	3.35	3.25		

TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT (K_1) AND SOLUTE AGGREGATIONS DATA FOR 1 : 1 MOLECULAR COMPLEXES OF SOME METAL ACETYLACETONATES WITH IODINE IN CARBON TETRACHLORIDE AT 30°

Complex	Equilibrium Constant (K_1) l. mole ⁻¹						SA _d	SA _a	
	Refractometric Methods								
	1	2	$\Delta\phi_a$ maxima	3	4	$\Delta\Omega_{CDA}$ maxima			5
Be(acac) ₃ -I ₂	40.50	33.76		28.93	20.72		19.23	10.22	10.77
Al(acac) ₃ -I ₂	390.11	191.50	0.45		179.20	0.42	183.00		
Fe(acac) ₃ -I ₂	454.11	309.00	0.50		245.79	0.48	269.18		
Cr(acac) ₃ -I ₂	918.26	842.00	0.68		842.87	0.66	892.35		
VO(acac) ₃ -I ₂	1063.15	918.00	0.68		918.26	0.69	897.42		
Co(acac) ₃ -I ₂	1287.18	1175.91	0.75		1063.47	0.72	1083.33		
Zr(acac) ₄ -I ₂	1445.10	1287.00	0.80		1175.91	0.74	1135.34		
Th(acac) ₄ -I ₂	2515.10	—	—		2118.12	0.91	2172.49		

1. Calculated from the plot of n^2 vs molar ratio of solutes.
2. Calculated from the plot of $\Delta\phi_a$ vs molar ratio of solutes.
3. Calculated from the plot of $\Delta\phi_d$ vs molar ratio of solutes.
4. Calculated from the plot of $\Delta\Omega_{CDA}$ vs molar ratio of solutes.
5. Calculated from the plot of $x_{D,T}$ vs $\Delta\phi_D/\Delta\phi_{DA}C_A^\circ$.

between $M(acac)_n$ and I_2 . The appreciable increase in these values has been interpreted due to the charge-transfer interaction between metal acetylacetonate rings and iodine.

The K_1 calculated for these complexes from equations (1-4) are listed in Table 1. From this table, it is clear that K_1 obtained from these equations are almost the same for strong complexes but different for weak and moderate complexes. These values are comparable with those obtained from spectroscopic method¹. Since for strong complexes, the concentration of solutes was kept low ($10^{-3}M$), the possibility of solute aggregation minimizes. The difference in K_1 thus noted may be due to the betterment of the respective equations. From this table, it is also evident that K_1 obtained from equation (1) in which refraction per cm³ due to solvent was considered, show maximum percentage of error. The concentration for Be(acac)₃ was raised ($10^{-2}M$). In this case, the K_1 calculated from equation (1) shows maximum percentage of error which minimizes when equations (2 and 3) were used. But the best values were observed when equation (4) was used. In this case we could get different k values when $\Delta\phi_a$ or $\Delta\phi_d$ was plotted against molar ratio of solutes (Table 2). For other cases [$M(acac)_n-I_2$, where $M=Al(III), Fe(III), Cr(III), Co(III), VO(IV), Zr(IV)$ and $Th(IV)$], it was not noted so. The

present study indicates that the contribution of refraction per cm³ of donor, acceptor and solvent is more important in weak and moderate complexes than that for strong complexes which is in good agreement with our earlier observations^{6,14}.

Since the complex is generally more polar than the components, the electronic polarizability or refractive index increases and the deviation depends upon the extent of interaction between donor and acceptor¹⁵⁻¹⁸. Therefore, stronger the complex greater would be the deviation in the refractive index value and weaker the complex smaller would be the deviation. The $\Delta\Omega_{CDA}$ maxima (Table 2) indicate the order of interaction in the following sequence :

This order of deviation is the same as the order of K_1 values noted for these systems. The values of α also increase with the increase in K_1 values. Thus, the omission of electronic polarizability in the theoretical derivation of dipole moment (μ) calculation, may create a problem to get its exact value as has been done earlier¹⁶⁻²².

The contribution of acceptor (SA_a) and donor (SA_d) in total 30% solute aggregation for Be(acac)₃-I₂ complex have been calculated using equations

8 and 9. These data indicate that the contribution of donor in total 30% solute aggregation is less than that of acceptor. This is in agreement with our earlier observations⁶.

Solute (Donor)-Solvent interaction: The K_1 calculated from equation (1) show more reliability than the K_1 calculated from the plot of n^2 vs molar ratio of solutes. This indicates that the role of solvent in these complexes cannot be ruled out. Since in equation (1) the difference in the refraction per cm^3 of solution and solvent ($\delta\phi$) was considered, in Yoshida and Osawa's method⁷, square of refractive index (n^2) of the solution (donor+acceptor) was taken into account. Therefore, this difference in K_1 values may be due to the solute-solvent [$M(\text{acac})_n - \text{CCl}_4$] interaction. Prausnitz *et al*²³⁻²⁵ have adduced evidence that CCl_4 behaves as an electron acceptor and forms complexes with aromatic hydrocarbons. Support for complex formation between benzene and CCl_4 also includes the results from measurements of volumes and heat of mixing²⁶⁻³⁰, from freezing point diagrams^{26,31-33}, and from far infrared spectroscopic measurements³⁴. These results have indicated that in aromatic hydrocarbon- CCl_4 complexes, π -pool of electrons of hydrocarbons donates the electron to CCl_4 ; K_1 for benzene- CCl_4 interaction were noted to be, $0.043 \pm 0.081 \text{ l.mol}^{-1}$. In case of $M(\text{acac})_n - \text{CCl}_4$ systems we could not measure the K_1 values in inert solvent (cyclohexane) due to the low solubility of $M(\text{acac})_n$. However, for $M(\text{acac})_n - \text{CCl}_4$ interactions, the K_1 values may be assumed to be very low because by plotting n^2 vs molar ratio of solutes, a slight deviation in k value for $\text{Be}(\text{acac})_2 - \text{CCl}_4$ system in cyclohexane was observed which indicated the low K_1 values for this type of interaction. Since, the value of k is almost of the same order as of benzene- CCl_4 system, therefore it indicates the same type of interaction in $M(\text{acac})_n - \text{CCl}_4$ system. Thus, it provides further evidence on the pseudo-aromatic character of $M(\text{acac})_n$ chelate rings.

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